

Fertilizer management

Response of rice hybrids to N sources and time of application of N and K

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Although $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ has been accepted as the preferred N source in rice, $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ was reported to be the preferred source in China at late crop growth stages when hybrid exhibited a peak demand for nutrients. A higher percentage of unfilled grains is common in hybrid rices unless the soil nutrient supply can cope with crop demands. Thus, delayed application of N and K coinciding with flowering can help realize the potential of hybrid rices.

We studied the differential response of recently released hybrids to various N sources and split application of N

and K. In a Vertisol (typical Pellustert), during the 1994 and 1996 wet season, four hybrids (MGR1, KRH1, APRH1, and APRH2) received the following N treatments: 120 kg ha⁻¹ at 33:33:33% at the basal, tillering, and flowering stages, respectively; and 120 kg ha⁻¹ likewise at the basal, tillering, plant initiation, and flowering stages. All phosphorus was applied basally (P at 26.4 kg ha⁻¹). Potash was either applied as basal or in two splits (75% basal and 25% at flowering). Data on grain and straw yields and their N uptake were recorded.

Of the two N sources tested, $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ was found to be superior for grain yield (5.3 t ha⁻¹) and N uptake (128 kg ha⁻¹). This indicated that the more stable $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ held by the soil cation exchange complex (CEC) affected yield. Although the usefulness of $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ for hybrids at the reproductive stage has

been reported, it leached and was unstable. Three equal N split applications were on a par with four N splits. Irrespective of N sources, a topdressing of N beyond the panicle initiation stage for short- and mid-duration groups did not bestow any additional yield advantage. Similarly, a split application of K (twice) did not affect either grain yield or N uptake even though an adequate K supply at flowering was known to improve grain filling via the efficient translocation of photosynthates to the sink. High levels of available K present at the experimental site might have taken care of the crop needs.

The present study indicated that $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ is a better source of N for hybrids. In Vertisols with a high CEC contributing to the retention of applied $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ and high available K status, there is no need to resort to delayed N and K application. ■

Nitrogen response of Karnataka Rice Hybrid 2

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The development of hybrids, because of their heterotic vigor, could increase rice productivity by breaking the yield barrier. With this objective, two rice hybrids—Karnataka Rice Hybrid 1 (KRH1) and Karnataka Rice Hybrid 2 (KRH2)—were released in Karnataka. Hybrids in most crops usually require an increased use of various nutrients, especially N.

To determine the N requirement in KRH2, a medium-duration rice hybrid, a study was undertaken using IR20 as a check variety. Experiments were laid out with different levels of N, ranging from 0 to 200 kg ha⁻¹, on a sandy loam soil with a pH of 6.5 and organic C of 0.5% in a split-plot design with three replications during the 1994-96 wet seasons.

KRH2 outyielded IR20 at all levels of N application, ranging from 0 to 200 kg ha⁻¹. In IR20, the tiller number was higher than that of KRH2. The increased yield of KRH2 was mainly attributed to the higher number of productive tillers, panicle weight, and number of filled grains. The nutrients

used for the production of unproductive tillers in IR20 might have been better used in KRH2 to increase seed set, panicle weight, and thus yield. IR20 responded to applied N only up to 100 kg ha⁻¹. In KRH2, the response to applied N beyond 100 kg ha⁻¹ was marginal and insignificant. ■

Integrated pest management — diseases

The effect of *Trichoderma* and antifungal agents on rice germination

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Rice seeds were found to exhibit very weak or no germination when sown in an antifungal seed-raising mix made by cultivating the forest green mold, *Trichoderma viride*, in nutrient-supplemented sawdust from *Pinus radiata* wood. (*P. radiata* is a common temperate plantation softwood that is grown extensively in southern

hemisphere countries for lumber.) *Trichoderma* is a genus of pathogenic fungi used widely in horticulture against such fungal diseases as silverleaf in fruit trees. The aim of the antifungal mix is to provide a natural control agent against damping down or seedling wilt diseases using a cheap and abundant plant waste.

Common vegetables (carrot, radish, lettuce, tomato) germinated and grew extremely well in the antifungal mix with no disease mortality. But when four rice varieties (IR60 HD 105, PSBRE4 HD 437, PSBRE2 HD 429, and PSBRC10 HD 439) were tried in the new